

HUANG JIEYUAN

IMAGE

FIELD

About Image Field

Image Field places images and physical entities to be examined in a hybrid type of space, such as physical as well as virtual space. It can be considered as a network structure of point clouds. image field is not a centralized project, instead it is discrete, while different organic components are interconnected and continuously evolving.

Image Field is a multi-faceted research ongoing project on images, their media and contexts, and is structured in a rhizome structure, with a core research module and several extension modules.

Within the core research module, Image Field embodies a number of strategies for intervening in the complex phenomenon of the contemporary digital image, and covers the study of mediation based on the screen space and the infrastructure on which media art is based through a number of **sub-projects**, which are a collection of different smaller sub-projects. These sub-projects cover a number of different directions and enable a certain degree of research to be achieved.

In addition to the core research module and as an extension, Image Field is a stand-alone visual space - **Image Field Space** - which is a virtual space for the visualisation of the project, allowing for the creation of a visualisation of Image Field in online web space and offline computer systems. The **Image Field Institute** is another section, the Institute, which refers to an online multi-functional venue that includes an archive database, a collaboration platform, a virtual gallery and more. In contrast to the above sectors, which are predominantly online and virtual, the **Image Field Zone** is a working area that extends into the physical space, an area where projects can be implemented on the ground in conjunction with the research and results of Image Field. In a new phase, there will also exist **Image Field Land**, Image Field's digital economy strategy, which seeks to build a new model of funding support for projects.

Within the above sections, Image Field presents several hybrid and intersecting compositional forms, including a two-dimensional internet website that acts as an access point for the project, multiple video works featuring the project's research, a virtual three-dimensional space capable of housing Image Field and related visual compositions, a digital archive that preserves the project's research process and related materials, a web-based web-based forum for multi-user communication and practice, and a workshop that can exist in a physical space, etc.

The aim of the project is to try to develop a new mode of operation for artistic practice and to provide within its framework an exploration of the media art environment and the role of the artist. In addition to focusing on the image and media context, Image Field also involves the conception of a new role for the artist, in which the artist becomes more of an initiator, promoter and fundraiser of a complex project. Further on, the artist is transformed into a virtual persona that can be operated by different users.

Image Field was launched at the end of 2020 and the first phase of its work, the implementation of the core research section, was carried out in early 2021 and is presented in Image Field - Intro. Image Field is currently in a new phase of construction, with Image Field Space, Image Field Institute and Image Field Zone all being implemented.

For more information, please visit <https://imagefield.art>

Image Field is a multi-faceted ongoing research project on images, their media and contexts, and is structured in a rhizome structure, with a core research module and several extension modules."

Conception of Image Field

Intro

screenshots from video

Intro is the part of the Image Field that is introduced by numerous works

,and it is also the intersection where the project's internal and external connections are made. It shows the progress of Image Field in several ways. For example, the portfolio, the website, the video series, and the presentation report. The portfolio acts as a basic archive document, allowing the project to be documented in a clearer way. As mentioned in the Image Field - Intro video, one of the ways to access the Image Field project is through the website. Throughout the project, the website is used for more than a simple showcase, it is given more functionality; the basic framework for the three modules - Image Field Space, Image Field Institute and Image Field Land - is based on the web and the website is the entry point to them, acting as an interface and as an area for me to work in. The video series will be divided in several different directions, such as the currently planned introductory video and the essay film/video essay, which will be oriented towards the presentation of ideas, and the progress of Image Field will be presented in the seminar and colloquium.

Intro is the part of the Image Field that is introduced by numerous works"

Image Field – Intro (Version 2020)

8K video, color, sound, 00:11:19, 2020

link: <https://vimeo.com/495250062>
Password: Intro

Subprojects

Labo Series

Medium Series

Nomad Series

Application Series

** The classification of subprojects is based on a intersectionality which reflects a cross-disciplinary and networked approach to work*

The core research module of Image Field is divided into several **research areas**, which are further divided into **sub-projects**. At this stage, images and media are used as the main object of research, and the branches of research will not be limited to the following examples, but will expand in scope as the research progresses, which is currently the main series:

1. Labo Series

2. Medium Series

3. Human Series

4. Nomad Series

5. Application Series

Labo DoS - Distribution of Screens (2020-)

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M

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IF SOLUTION (Concept) (2020-)

M

A

Outdoor Survival Suit for Video Installation (2020)

M

N

A

Hacking the TV test video (2020)

L

M

Oasiscreen (2020)

M

N

A

High Water (2021)

M

N

A

Building Backup (2020)

N

A

Laboratory Reconstruction-Artist Guided Project (2021)

L

A

Reports from Daily Analysis (2020-2021)

A

Labo DoS - Distribution of Screens (2020-)

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Labo DoS - Distribution of Screens

Both the field of view and the frame have limitations, but the field of view is the domain of human vision and can change as people move, while the frame is the material domain of the image, which is in a relatively stable state (but flexible screens break the stability of the frame). Since it reflects the most intuitive aspects of viewing behavior, observation and experimentation on the range of the field of view and the screen frame are the first issues to be addressed by Labo Series.

Labo was mentioned above as a conceptual "laboratory" because Labo does not need to be confined to a specific form, it can be a laboratory in a physical space or a laboratory in a virtual space, according to the way I practice art. In the design of the experiments and in fact, I will refer to some principles and methods that need to be considered for scientific experiments. Labo's experimental objects are Image and Field, Labo's experimental elements exist in various combinations of Image and Field, its variables need to be in "static-dynamic", " digital and non-digital". Labo's experimental effects are defined in relationships such as "single screen - set of screens - set of screens across time and space", "centralized - discrete", etc. The experimental effects of Labo need to consider the combination of different elements and the degree to which they are combined. The design of the experiment will not be presented here for the time being, as it involves many non-artistic aspects. Therefore, technologists in the relevant fields will be invited to collaborate in the implementation process.

Study case 01 example of Labo DoS (2020)

Transmission of images across space through the network
concept based on **digital signage** work flow

Image transmission path:

- computer
- digital signage server
- screens in urban spaces
- screens in outdoor natural spaces

IF SOLUTION (Concept) (2020-)

With inspiration from the Open Source Hardware Association (OSHW), I began to think about a way to get the right design for the media and technology in the Image Field, the IF Solution, which stands for Image Field Solution and consists of a number of features proposed in Image Field project. IF Solution means "the solution of the medium". IF Solution is to place the design and optimization of media and technologies carried out in Image Field in a co-creative platform that is not only my responsibility, but also accessible to different participants. Here I refer to the concept of Latour's project <http://modesofexistence.org/>. It establishes the research project as a media platform rather than a closed working group, so that the institution of a project becomes a mediated institution.

Outdoor Survival Suit for Video Installation (concept) (2020-)

Oasiscreen (2020-)

When a collection of screens across time and space can be used flexibly, even screens in vehicles, for example, can be designed into the playback process, the image has gained a full spatio-temporal mobility. Oasiscreen, as a combination of the two, attempts to bring the image to different environments, such as the natural environment, where video technology does not exist. Using a solution consisting of solar panels, protective enclosures, wireless modules for cellular networks, smart players and screens, the images can be continuously transferred from other locations to video installations in deserts and similar harsh environments. The project expects the video installation to be sustainable as a plant in the desert, forming a digital video oasis. In other versions, the device can be designed in different scenarios.

The emergence of media art is first and foremost the result of technological progress, and I need to first define the range of media I am dealing with to refer to the media involved in media art, rather than to a broad range of all media. The invention and popularization of photography, radio, and television, and the formation of a new consumer society laid the foundation for the technical and cultural conditions for the creation of video art. At the same time, the rise of rebellion and extremist consciousness, student movements, feminism, the sexual revolution and other social conditions inspired and facilitated the rise of video art; the early rise of video art also stemmed from the rebellion against commercial television. Along with the background of image culture and television culture, the medium of media art has undergone multiple evolutions since the advent of Fluxus in the 1960s, from the first analog technology, to digital technology, then computers, and more recently to artificial intelligence technology. Avant-garde media art has always used the image technology of the time while challenging the established media-illustrative frameworks, as well as the ideologies and social mechanisms that dominate the medium, and giving the medium a new perception and scope. The above briefly introduces the background of the development of media and technology in video art. Media art relies on pictorial media, but what does the medium of media rely on?

If we look deeper, like Trevor Paglen's search for the cables that support the global flow of data at the bottom of the ocean, what lies beneath the media art is an invisible power grid buried underground, with the source of the interlocking cables being the monopoly power system. Such a power system is rooted in industrial production that consumes a lot of fossil fuels, and despite the propaganda of the power companies to increase the use of green energy, this process will take a long time; control, a fundamental shift cannot be made in a short period of time. So a fundamental consideration of the mechanisms by which images operate can look at the mode of electricity supply, and consider whether media art can be separated from the electrical system and be able to operate on its own. In Oasiscreen, the collection of images is taken outside the city into the wasteland, the vacuum of electricity, and I take the opportunity to develop a way out of the electrical system. In the combination of IF Solution and Oasiscreen, I referenced the use of small solar panels and sought to find a suitable solution to the electricity supply. From this perspective, I gradually developed a more thoughtful approach to electricity and tried to integrate it into Oasiscreen's framework, as Oasiscreen's geographic area of interest intersects with that of electricity scarcity.

Oasiscreen combines cloud-based delivery and management technologies to control and adapt variable content to different playback environments and contexts, so it is a non-fixed video device that can operate independently in an un-powered environment. The focus of Oasiscreen's practice in electricity is how to generate a stand-alone, ecological approach to power generation that can be deeply integrated with Oasiscreen.

Oasiscreen is the artist's expanded conception of the image's mobility under the concept of "image domain". Based on the operation and experiment of the image, the artist expands the scope of thinking to how digital images are in the real environment. Being able to exist is what constitutes the basis of their existence, and this leads to the concept of a "non-fixed, sustainable image installation".

It is intended to break the fixedness of traditional video installations, such as venue restrictions, fixed play sequences and other factors. The artist tried to combine video technology in different fields. Among them, the artist critically introduced the technology of digital signage into the structure of the device, allowing key technologies such as network transmission, cloud content management server and open player to reconstruct the loop from video production to playback. Artists can use the computer to make images remotely, upload the content to the cloud content management server, and transfer the content to the intelligent playback terminal through the network. Images can be continuously generated and transmitted to a flexible screen at any time.

When the screen can be used flexibly, even when the screen in the vehicle can be designed into the playback process, the image has been fully mobile. At the same time, the artist takes sustainability as another direction of thinking. As a combination of the two, Oasis Screen attempts to bring images into harsh environments that are not suitable for digital images to survive. With a solar panel, protective casing, cellular network wireless module, smart player, and screen, the image can be continuously transmitted from other places to the image device in the desert or similar harsh environment. This project expects that video installations, like plants, can grow sustainably in the desert, forming a digital image oasis. At the same time, a shooting device connected to the Internet is installed in front of the device, constantly monitoring the device, so the viewing behavior can not happen on the scene. The control terminal and the monitoring terminal are arranged in a new space, and the viewer can become the content publisher and viewer of this group of video devices without having to be on the scene of playing the video.

Oasiscreen(2020)

dust- and waterproof screen, Raspberry Pi player, Solar panel, variable size, 2020

left and above installation view

Oasiscreen - Desert Monitoring (2020)

LCD screen, waterproof metal box with glass, Raspberry Pi with waterproof case, cellular module and camera module, player based on Raspberry Pi, solar panel, multi-panel video

variable size, video looping, 2020

above and left
installation view

High Water (2021)

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High Water is a project about a “live streaming based on live streaming”. The artist collected several live video feeds of water, such as rivers, lakes, oceans, etc., and used screen recording software to add information about the location, geography and distance from the viewer in front of the live feed. The multiple layers of images were then streamed to the exhibition site screen for a second time. Although the image is real-time flow of water, the viewing of water becomes an unrealistic cross-screen and cross-space behavior, and in the scene, the audience must look up at the screen, instead of looking down at the water, as we are used to.

1 / Camera

3 / view of the river

High Water (2021)

Live video streaming, screen recording software, computer, screen, video live broadcasting, variable size, 2021

2 / Shooting and live streamig

4 / re-live-streaming and reproduction of the resource

The screen for viewing is placed on a high position and information about all live channels is printed on the wall next to it. The screen is marked with the geographical information of the live broadcast at that location and the geographical information of all live sources will be printed on the wall.

Malsch Germany 48°54'29.4"N 8°18'45.1"E 48.908160, 8.312513

Building Backup (2020)

... eine Fabrik verschwindet

Die Geschichte und das Ende
der Portland-Cementfabrik Blaubeuren

publications

...eine Fabrik verschwindet
Die Geschichte und das Ende
der Portland-Cementfabrik Blaubeuren

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Backups of buildings are concerned with re-excavating archives as image clusters and creating new images from them, and virtual backups of buildings or other things are exactly what image research is all about across images and dimensions.

Archived pictures from publications

Hidden Flow-Cement Plant is the first experimental video of the artist's virtual series. The virtual state refers to things that are completely destroyed or damaged at the physical level and then rebuilt at the virtual level. The virtual state includes avatars composed of specific images in the real world, as well as model reconstruction of things in the virtual three-dimensional world.

The artist thinks about how material exists in the digital environment, so this series is produced. The material virtual state series attempts to combine two research directions, namely digital archaeology and image archiving. The artist attempts to collect images from the Internet through archaeological excavation and archive a digital image of the resume. Archived images in reality are also introduced as another form of images. In addition, the virtual model is another kind of image avatar, which looks tangible, but it is actually another form of image. The existence of the image is established and becomes a virtual state parallel to things, more like a hidden image flow.

As the first work, Hidden Flow-Cement Plant examines the historical pictures of the Heidelberg Cement Plant in Germany. Based on a picture of a factory site that has been demolished, the virtual state of the cement plant is reconstructed. The cement plant has been given the meaning of construction, so this video is also a metaphor for the existence and circulation of things.

Hidden Flow - Cement Plant (2020)

8K video, 32:9, color, no sound, 00:02:07, loop, 2020

link:

<https://vimeo.com/389757104>

Password: Cementplant

screenshots from video

Laboratory Reconstruction -Artist Guided Project (2021)

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This project is a video work for the workshop Labor 2025, a collaboration between the Fraunhofer Institute for Electronic Nanosystems and Klub Solitaer e.V. in Germany, and as part of the Ars Electronica Center's exhibition CCI Lab. The workshop attempts to reflect that scientific and artistic research each have very different ways in their practices: While scientific protocols are based on the idea of repeatability in a laboratory, the relevance of the artist is in the creation of unrepeatable pieces that are then sold to elite clientele. The purpose of this project is hence to rebut these myths, by finding the shared goals and interests of scientific and artistic practices, protocols and rituals. The materials and experiences collected over the process of the workshop are presented to generate a new territory where all fields can reflect together through a joint aesthetic experience the nuances of their work, eventually finding new and unexpected links to other, diametrically opposed, practices.

The project takes a visual-spatial-logical perspective on the strictly protected environment of technological inventions and production in the field of science. As certain spaces become an inaccessible and distant presence, the ability to peer into and restore a space through multiple visual materials is a complex problem caught between the public domain and the closed scientific laboratory.

Artist HUANG Jieyuan and ZHOU Yinglin tried to simulate the space through multiple images obtained in the workshop, combined with many fragments of information that existed in the corners of the Internet, and gained the power to freely visit the virtual space. In this space, the tour conducted by the laboratory staff can become a tour conducted by the artist, and the laboratory space and the production of science and technology are embodied in another narrative way.

Laboratory Reconstruction-Artist Guided Project

Full HD digital video, color, sound, 00:03:30, 2021

link:

<https://vimeo.com/597278376>

Password: Lab2021

screenshots from video

Reports from Daily Analysis (2020-2021)

There has never been a time when the impact of digitalization and virtualization has been as profound as it is now, when technologized and digital controls have been adopted in large numbers behind worldwide public health emergencies, when the scope of everyday life has been replaced by cyberspace, and when digital meetings have become the new everyday. The fact that these technologies often take over our lives before we fully understand the workings and risks behind them requires a brake-like move to make us rethink our relationship with technology.

In cooperation with A4 Art Museum

Digital Virtual Technology and Private Sphere Vol. 01 (2021)

Artist-led curating Project, 2021

Digital Virtual Technology and Private Sphere – a Collective Critical Report is a practice in which participants engage in a critical process of daily digital life through their own digitization, virtualization, observation, analysis, and comparison of cases. This work will be implemented by each participant in the form of images, graphics, text, audio, etc. The project will be carried out at different scales. The project will explore the topic of digital virtualization from a private perspective on a variety of scales, and these “private reports” will constitute a collection of profiled images in the overall project, which is a combination of an open platform and a community of images.

Participants conduct a private “daily analysis practice of digitization and virtualization” of themselves and simultaneously records, based on a private starting point, in a manner of personal choice. I need to try to find a logical way to combine and further integrate the members’ initial “private reports” into a collective community.

Digital Virtual Technology and Private Sphere is a long-term ongoing research project, and the Report is the first project to focus on a combined online and offline exhibition format, and includes a project website, project manual, video module, and online and on-site exhibitions.

The project is supported by the Ya project of the A4 Art Museum (Chengdu) in terms of platform and exhibition.

Project Components:

- 1) Huang Jieyuan, Digital Virtual Technology and Private Sphere Vol. 01, 4K Video, Single Screen, Color, With Sound, 4'0", 2020
- 2) Digital Virtual Technology and Private Sphere - A Collective Critical Report project team, Digital Virtual Technology and the Private Sphere - A Collective Critical Report Booklet, project book, 210 mm × 148 mm, 2020.
- 3) Digital Virtual Technology and Private Sphere - A Collective Critical Report project team, <https://digitalvirtualreport.cargo.site/>, website, hosted on the site building platform, 2020.
- 4) Digital Virtual Technology and Private Sphere - A Collective Critical Report project team, Digital Virtual Technology and the Private Sphere - A Collective Critical Report Trailer, HD video, single screen, color, with sound, 2'24", 2020
- 5) Individual report section:
 - i. Chen Mengxi, "When Covid-19 comes. Dancers started live broadcasting. I call it "Entertainment circle ", Single Channel Video Installation, Record of online live broadcasting talk, 3'41", 2020
 - ii. Li Linxi, Hold your head and comb your hair, video, 2'43", 2020
 - iii. Yukii Li, Private Customized Online Shopping Experience For You, Participatory interaction, 2020
 - iv. Zapkin Wen, Instantaneously Post Your Hate Button, Interactive installation, 2020
 - v. Charlotte Yao, Safe word undefined, if you're happy and you know it clap your hands, video, 5'55", 2020
 - vi. Zhou Yinglin, 4k video, 2-channel, color, sound, 3'59", 2020

Digital Virtual Technology and Private Sphere Vol. 02 (2021)

Artist-led curating Project, 2021

Report of Digital Virtual Technology and the Private Sphere an exercise in which participants complete a process similar to the critique of everyday digital life through digging, observing, analyzing, and comparing cases involving their own digitization and virtualization. The work will be carried out by each participant in the form of video, image, text, audio, etc. These "private reports" constitute a collection of dissected images in the overall project, which is a combination of an open platform and a community of images.

Each participant performs a private "daily practice of digital virtualization analysis" and records it, based on a private starting point, in a way that is personally chosen. I need to try to find a reasonable combination and further integrate and compile the initial "private reports" of each member into a collective image community.

Vol.02 builds on the previous project, focusing on the nuances of digital virtual technology and related issues.

The project is supported by the Yanjiao Biennale in terms of platform and exhibition.

Keywords for the project report:

Digital Voice - Albert Negredo, Selina Lee

Digital Geography - Aurelie Crisetig, Pedro Gramaxo

Digital and Behavior - Cherrie Yu, Çifel Hüseyin

Technology and the Body - Emin Mathers, Marcel Top

The Virtual and the Spatial - Zhou Yinglin, Pastel White, Li Yijun

project exhibition poster 2021

report catalog

Project Components:

1) Albert Negredo, UNUSUAL, HD Video, Single Screen, Color, Sound, 00:02:18, 2019

2) Aurelie Crisetig, This belongs to everyone, so enjoy the view, digital photography, digital image, collage, size variable, 2020.

3) Cherrie Yu, Trio A, HD Video, Single Screen, Color, Sound, 00:36:39, 2020.

4) Çifel Hüseyin, Artistically Exploring "Distance" as a Transformative Dimension, Arduino microcontrollers, cameras, computers, drawing robots, size variable, 2020

5) Emin Mathers, Human of 2020, digital photography, size variable, 2020.

6) Li Yijun, Dairy Dream Factory, CG animation, 2k video, single screen, sound, 00:01:43, 2020.

7) Marcel Top, Inferences, HD Video, GAN, data, digital images, size variable, 2020.

8) Pastel White, The Still Life, digital photography, virtual CGI scenes, size variable, 2020.

9) Pedro Gramaxo, Portrait#5, digital photography, size variable, 2020.

10) Selina Lee, Fox News in Chinese, Video, box, voice assistant, news video, size variable, 2020

11) Zhou Yinglin, Square Deception, 4k video, Single Screen, Color, Sound, 00:03:59, 2020.

In the year The Translated From China's 1962 dance film with a series of performances. The participants each had a novel gesture through the original dance film's reference scene, which we marked with the digital new movement. In the order of appearance, I had health, a former dancer with the Mexico Contemporary Company, Shuang Shuang, a former of classical ballet training, from Beijing, a former Chicago dancer, and the teacher. The project was developed during the 2020 pandemic and of illness recovery in each performer's house. The individual dance was accompanied by the apartment making their personal stories.

right online exhibition view

Image Field Space

Image Field is also a visual space - Image Field Space - which is the project's visualisation virtual space that allows a visualisation of Image Field in online web space as well as in offline computer systems.

A rendering of the 3D generated virtual space

Image Field Space is still under construction and is only available in limited technical form as an early version online.

Image Field Space early build demo

<https://imagefield.xyz/Image-Field-Space>

Image Field Zone

IMAGE 图像 FIELD 域 ZONE 地带

BEYOND GEOGRAPHY 超越地理

"Image Field Zone" refers to a workspace that extends into physical space, a workspace where projects can be implemented in situ in relation to the research and results of Image Field. Based on Image Field's practice of media, contexts, virtual spaces, archives, project collaboration platforms, etc. around images, the Image Field Zone is further transformed into a working area in physical space, specifically referred to as "The Zone". In the version presented here, the Image Field Zone is conceived as an 'image workflow', or a 'system' for the flow of images.

"Image Field Zone" refers to a workspace that extends into physical space, a workspace where projects can be implemented in situ in relation to the research and results of Image Field."

At the heart of the Image Field Zone is a set of multi-stage workflows around images. The Zone is divided into five main sections, R, H, T, N and X.

R (Resource) is a source of unprocessed images, partly provided by the artist and partly provided by the viewer, in which the images begin to flow and enter the work system in a combined image interactivity.

The H (Human Human) refers to the operator involved in the system and is responsible for linking the various parts of the workflow together. The operator will integrate the images in the database and will be responsible for the smooth distribution of the data content processed by the artist to the next stage.

The T (Terminal) is the core of the Image Field Zone and is controlled by the H (Human) section of the staff, which includes the image library, image playback, simulation of the Image Field virtual world, operation of the web content manager and much more.

The N (Nature) component has two specific dimensions, one concerned with integrating digital media installations into nature and operating independently of the natural environment using sustainable energy sources. The other dimension is the construction of another nature in the virtual world, which is derived as a virtual entity in digital form, showing a richness similar to that of nature.

X (Archive X) is an archival process for images that have already finished their run in the system. It aims to use the image database already generated in the system, the virtual form of the image, and the new "nature" generated from the image as a basis for archiving, thus creating a new archival direction.

"图像域地带-超越地理"是一个艺术家提出的长期持续研究项目"图像域"所驱动的实验项目。该项目建立了一个基于图像的工作系统，并在其中引入对图像的流转、形态转化、图像和空间的关系等方面的实验。"图像域地带-超越地理"同时也是一个融合了虚拟技术、数据库、数据生成艺术以及影像的综合新媒体装置。

"图像域地带"指的是一个能够延伸至物理空间的工作地带，一个能够结合"图像域"涉及的研究和成果，将项目进行在地实施的工作区。（参考：Image Field <https://imagefield.art>）
基于艺术家对图像域的媒介、语境、虚拟空间、档案、项目合作平台等方面的实践。"图像域地带"进一步将其转化为一个处于物理空间的工作区域。该工作区域被具体称为"地带"。它可以被理解为一种能够在本地化操作和本地化转化的模块工作区域，它可以运用来自Image Field的不同方式和策略进行工作。因此它的形态是可变的。在本次呈现的原本中，"图像域地带"被设想为一个"图像 workflow"，或者一个"图像流转"的"系统"，该系统被分为5个部分，分别由R、H、T、N、X代表：

R (Resource) 提供图像的输出，一部分可以由艺术家提供，另一部分则由观众提供。
H (Human 人类) 指的是系统中参与工作的操作员，它负责连接工作流程中各个部分的前端。
T (Terminal 终端) 是Image Field Zone的核心部分，它包括图像库、图像播放、虚拟世界的模拟、对网络内容管理器的操作等等。
N (Nature 自然) 具体指的是在虚拟世界中构建另一重数字化的自然，该自然被引为一种数字形态的虚拟实体。
X (Archive X 档案X) 是对已经在系统中运行结束的图像进行的存档处理，它旨在实验新的存档方式。

"超越地理"是"图像域地带"落地的第一个实施计划。"图像域地带-超越地理"依托于"图像域地带"所规划的工作系统，引入了图像与地理、空间的关系、制图学与数字地理信息系统和图像分类学等问题。具体来说，艺术影响着图像地理，空间能够如何组合起来创造新的有机体，并在制图学和数字地理信息系统等具体应用方面提出新的可能性，以艺术研究项目的方法展开相关讨论。此外，在引入图像资源的同时，基于传统信息分类学的图像分类也带来了许多问题，因此"超越地理"也是对于图像地理信息分类的实验。

- 01 Resource 图源
- 02 Human 人类
- 03 Terminal 终端
- 04 Nature 自然
- 05 Archive X 档案X

Image Field Zone - Beyond Geography
is the concept for the first case of Image Field Zone

above
installation view

right
Online image database
of Image Field Zone

Image Field Zone - Beyond Geography (concept) (2021-)

Image Field Zone - Beyond Geography is an experimental project driven by a long-term ongoing research project "Image Field" proposed by the artist, which creates a system of image-based work and introduces experiments on the flow of images, morphological transformations, the relationship between images and space. The project creates a system of image-based work in which experiments are introduced on the flow of images, morphological transformations, the relationship between images and space. It is also an integrated new media installation combining virtual technology, databases, data-generated art and video.

Image Field Zone - Beyond Geography builds on the system of work planned for "Image Field Zone" and introduces a reflection on the relationship between image and geography, space, cartography and digital GIS and image taxonomy. Specifically, the artist considers how images and geography and space can be combined to create new organic combinations and proposes new possibilities for specific applications such as cartography and digital GIS, which are discussed in the context of an artistic research project. In addition to the introduction of image resources, the classification of images based on traditional information taxonomy poses many problems, so "Beyond Geography" is also an experiment in the classification of image geographic information. The basic structure of "Image Field Zone - Beyond Geography" is based on the introduction of different image sources (R) with geo-information annotations into the project's operating system and their transmission via hub terminals (T) to the virtual space (V) and to the outdoor space outside the exhibition venue (N), where the viewer as a participant (H) is required to provide the diversity of the images, while the operator (H) is responsible for processing the image material and distributing the content created by the artist to the various sections. Finally, the images in the database will form an experimental physical archive (X), depending on the direction of the project's work.

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Online databases, computer programs based on the Unity virtual engine, video with immersive projection, Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) generated images, virtual terrain generated from GIS information, computers and cabinets, smartphones, screens, Led fluorescent lamps, iron shelves, books, printed images on paper, printers, archive cabinets, frames,

size variable, 2021

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installation view